

PROCESS INTENSIFICATION AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF ULTRASOUND-ASSISTED EXTRACTION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM *HANDELIA TRICHOPHYLLA***Tojiboeva D.,**

ORCID 0009-0009-6773-0749

Dusmatova D.,

ORCID 0009-0009-3644-0001

Mamatkhanova M.,**Mukhamatkhanova R.**

ORCID 0009-0004-2886-0798

Department of Terpenoids and Phenolic Compounds Chemistry,
S. Yunusov Institute of the Chemistry of Plant Substances,
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
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Abstract

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is an effective approach for process intensification in the recovery of bioactive compounds from plant materials. In this study, the extraction of biologically active compounds from the aerial parts of *Handelia trichophylla* was investigated and compared with conventional hot maceration (HM) from a chemical engineering perspective. The processes were evaluated in terms of extraction yield, processing time, and energy efficiency.

UAE was performed at 150 W and 40 kHz for 25 min, while HM was carried out at 50 °C for 24 h under identical solvent conditions (96% ethanol, solid–liquid ratio 1:10). UAE provided a higher extraction yield (11.2 ± 0.99%) compared to HM (8.4 ± 0.74%), corresponding to an intensification factor of 1.33. The process time was reduced by a factor of 57.6.

The total energy consumption for UAE was 0.0625 kWh, with a specific energy consumption of 0.56 kWh/kg. In contrast, HM required significantly higher energy input (7.2–12.0 kWh), resulting in a 150–250-fold increase in specific energy consumption. The energy efficiency index ($EEI = Y/E$) increased from 0.70–1.17 (HM) to 179.2 (UAE), demonstrating a substantial improvement in process performance.

The results confirm that UAE enables simultaneous enhancement of mass transfer and reduction of energy demand due to cavitation-induced cell disruption. The proposed approach highlights the potential of UAE as an energy-efficient and scalable technology for the extraction of plant-derived bioactive compounds.

Keywords: ultrasound-assisted extraction; process intensification; energy efficiency; maceration; *Handelia trichophylla*

Introduction

The extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials is a key operation in chemical, pharmaceutical, and biotechnological industries. Conventional extraction techniques, such as maceration, are characterized by slow diffusion rates, long processing times, and high energy consumption. These limitations necessitate the development of process intensification strategies in extraction technologies.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) has emerged as an effective method for process intensification. The enhancement of extraction efficiency in UAE is attributed to acoustic cavitation, which promotes cell disruption, improves solvent penetration, and accelerates mass transfer. From a chemical engineering perspective, the performance of extraction processes should be evaluated not only in terms of yield but also considering energy consumption and process efficiency. Ultrasound-assisted extraction can be considered an effective process intensification strategy.

Handelia trichophylla is the sole species of the monotypic genus *Handelia* Heimerl (Asteraceae). The plant is regarded as both ornamental and medicinal and has been traditionally used for the treatment of digestive disorders and fever [1].

На основе жидкого экстракта цветков *Handelia trichophylla* создано средство с противовоспалительным и спазмолитическим действием [2 —3].

A preparation with anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic activity has been developed based on a liquid extract of the flowers of *Handelia trichophylla* [4].

Handelia trichophylla is a source of biologically active terpenoids and phenolic compounds with potential pharmaceutical applications [5 —7].

However, despite growing interest in this plant, the energy efficiency of its extraction processes has not been previously investigated.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate the process intensification and energy efficiency of UAE in comparison with conventional hot maceration. Special attention is given to extraction yield, energy consumption, and energy efficiency indicators.

Materials and Methods**Plant Material**

The aerial parts of *Handelia trichophylla* were collected during the flowering period in the Jizzakh region (Uzbekistan). The plant was identified using herbarium specimens stored in the Central Herbarium of Uzbekistan (No. 5296).

Extraction Procedures

Hot maceration (HM) was performed using 96% ethanol at a solid–liquid ratio of 1:10, at 50 °C for 24 h with periodic stirring.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) was carried out under identical solvent conditions using an ultrasonic bath (150 W, 40 kHz) at 45 °C for 25 min.

All experiments were performed in triplicate. Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test ($n = 3$, $p \leq 0.05$).

Determination of Extraction Yield

The extraction yield was calculated as:

$$Y = \frac{m_{\text{extract}}}{m_{\text{raw}}} \times 100,$$

where m_{extract} - mass of dry extract; m_{raw} - mass of raw plant material.

The yields were:

- HM: $8.4 \pm 0.74\%$
- UAE: $11.2 \pm 0.99\%$

Energy Analysis

Total energy consumption was calculated as:

$$E = P \times t,$$

where

- E - energy consumption (kWh)
- P - power of the equipment (kW)
- t - process time (h)

For UAE:

$$E_{\text{UAE}} = 0.15 \times 0.417 = 0.0625 \text{ kWh}$$

Specific energy consumption:

$$E_{\text{spec}} = \frac{E}{m_{\text{extract}}},$$

where E_{spec} – specific energy consumption (kWh/kg).

$$E_{\text{spec,UAE}} = \frac{0.0625}{0.112} = 0.56 \text{ kWh/kg}$$

For hot maceration, energy consumption was estimated based on typical heating power (0.3–0.5 kW):

$$E_{\text{HM}} = 7.2\text{--}12.0 \text{ kWh}$$

$$E_{\text{spec, HM}} = 85.7\text{--}142.9 \text{ kWh/kg}$$

Energy efficiency index:

$$EEI = \frac{Y}{E},$$

where EEI – a energy efficiency index;

Y – yield of extractive substances (%);

E – energy consumption (kWh).

Statistical Analyses

The results are presented as mean values (M) ± standard deviation (SD). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test ($n = 3$). The intensification factor (K_{int}), acceleration factor (K_t), energy consumption coefficient (K_E), and energy efficiency index (IE) were calculated based on the average values of extraction yield and energy consumption.

The graphical representation (Figure 1) was generated based on experimental data and interpolated values for visualization purposes.

Results and Discussion

From a process engineering perspective, the significant improvement observed in UAE can be attributed to enhanced mass transfer mechanisms. Acoustic cavitation leads to the formation and collapse of microbubbles, generating localized high-pressure gradients that disrupt plant cell structures. This reduces internal diffusion resistance and shifts the extraction mechanism from diffusion-controlled to convection-enhanced mass transfer.

The key aspects of the energy efficiency of ultrasound-assisted extraction include specific energy consumption, the cavitation mechanism, preservation of thermolabile compounds, and environmental sustainability [8–11].

Ultrasound-assisted extraction resulted in a higher yield (11.2%) compared to hot maceration (8.4%), corresponding to a 33% increase in extraction efficiency. In addition, the extraction time was reduced from 24 h to 25 min, indicating a significant intensification of the process.

The comparative characteristics of hot maceration (HM) and ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Comparison of extraction methods for *Handelia trichophylla*

Method	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Specific energy consumption (kWh/kg)	Energy efficiency index (EEI)
Hot maceration	8.4 ± 0.74	1440	7.2–12.0*	85.7–142.9	0.7–1.2
Ultrasound extraction	11.2 ± 0.99	25	0.0625	0.56	179.2

*Calculated for heating power 0.3–0.5 kW.

UAE also demonstrated superior energy performance. The total energy consumption was 0.0625 kWh, whereas hot maceration required 7.2–12.0 kWh. The specific energy consumption for UAE (0.56 kWh/kg) was significantly lower than that for HM (85.7–142.9 kWh/kg), corresponding to a reduction factor of 150–250.

The energy efficiency index increased from 0.70–1.17 (HM) to 179.2 (UAE), confirming a substantial improvement in process performance. These results in-

dicate strong potential for scale-up and industrial implementation of ultrasound-assisted extraction processes.

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between extraction yield and energy consumption. The curve demonstrates a nonlinear dependence, where high yields are achieved at low energy input (UAE region), followed by a plateau at higher energy consumption levels (HM region). The intermediate values were interpolated for visualization purposes and reflect the general trend of the process.

Figure 1. Dependence of extraction yield on energy consumption for UAE and HM

To better illustrate the relationship between energy consumption and extraction yield, intermediate data points were interpolated based on the experimental values. The resulting curve demonstrates a nonlinear dependence, where the extraction yield increases sharply at low energy input (UAE region) and gradually approaches a plateau at higher energy consumption (maceration region).

The curve suggests an exponential-type dependence between energy consumption and extraction yield.

Conclusions

Ultrasound-assisted extraction of bioactive compounds from *Handelia trichophylla* demonstrates clear advantages over conventional hot maceration in terms of process intensification and energy efficiency.

The application of ultrasound resulted in:

- a 33% increase in extraction yield;
- a 57.6-fold reduction in extraction time;
- a 150–250-fold reduction in specific energy consumption;
- a significant increase in the energy efficiency index.

These results confirm that UAE is a promising strategy for the development of energy-efficient and scalable extraction processes for plant-derived bioactive compounds.

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Authors’ contributions

Durdona Sh. Tojiboeva: Conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing – original draft. Dilnoza E. Dusmatova: Data curation, formal analysis, validation. Munirakhon A. Mamatkhanova: Experimental work, resources, visualization. Rimma F. Mukhamatkhanova: Supervision, project administration, writing – review & editing.

Competing Interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing financial or non-financial interests.

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